

THE ROLE OF OBSERVATION IN LINGUISTIC TYPOLOGY.

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Summary: *The article deals with an observation, which is considered to be one of the methods of typological investigations. Observation is included as a necessary element in the procedure of any linguistic method and technique.*

Key words: *interpretation and classification, scientific analysis, unique, methods of cognition, comparative-historical method*

The method of linguistic observation and description, or descriptive method. It is the main method of language research. This method involves identifying specific language phenomena and describing them consistently in terms of their functioning.

The components of the descriptive method are observation, generalization, interpretation and classification. At the same time, the generalization boils down to the synthesis of similar and repeated phenomena, observation units into one broader category, within which they are combined by certain features - for example, the distribution of vocabulary into thematic, terminological, synonymous, and other groups.[1].

The increasing interest in the method of scientific analysis is caused by the rapid and at the same time uneven development of science and technology, the emergence of branches of knowledge at the intersection of different sciences. In these conditions, studying the rules and possibilities of transferring knowledge and methods of scientific analysis of one science to another becomes an urgent task.[2].

To realize the scientific knowledge of the reality surrounding us, its properties and laws, it is necessary to study it, that is, to determine its basic properties and establish the legislative connections that are enclosed in it.

Means of understanding nature and society is a system of certain techniques developed by centuries-old human practice and usually called the method. The method is a certain approach to reality, a certain path of knowledge of nature and society.[3].

Methods of cognition can be general and specific. Therefore, we can talk about a philosophical method, that is, a method (or way) of cognition in general; methodology in this case will be understood as compliance with the principles of the method of cognition inherent in a particular philosophical system. We can also talk about a general scientific method and understand methodology as a doctrine of

method and understand methodology as a doctrine of research methods characteristic of a particular science or group of sciences.[4].

The methodology of sciences is a concretization of the philosophical method of cognition as applied to the uniqueness of the objects being studied and a generalization of the methods and techniques developed in a particular science.

The method of cognition of a given phenomenon is a certain sum of scientific provisions and purely practical techniques, thanks to the use of which we get the opportunity to better and more comprehensively study a given phenomenon.

The dialectical method recognizes that the world is material, matter is primary, consciousness is secondary, the world is knowable. The phenomena of objective reality are interconnected, interdependent, but they are also in motion and development.[5].

Although the dialectical method is the general basis of the methodology of all sciences, nevertheless, each science, due to the specificity of the object of study, develops its own specific private methods and techniques of research. Thus, artificial satellites of the Earth are the greatest scientific achievement, but over time they have become a means of the experimental method of research. Linguistics, like any other science, creates its own methods of research and description of phenomena and facts of language, since the object of study of this science is precisely language. Language is a very complex and, moreover, multifaceted social phenomenon. It has a multi-tiered structure in which each tier, or, as they often say, level, consists of its own units, the study of which requires the development of its own, special system of techniques. Here we are talking about the phonological, morphological, syntactic, lexical levels.

The various states of language in the process of its development created favorable ground for the emergence of a scientifically very precise and convincing in its results comparative-historical method, which played such an important role in the development of the science of language. The basis of this method is the doctrine of the genetic relationship of a number of languages, which receives its material expression in the commonality of the sound form, as well as the position on the regular changes in the phonological system, in the grammatical structure and in the vocabulary of the related languages under study.[6].

In addition, in linguistics, the most common method of scientific research is linguistic observation.

The method of linguistic observation presupposes a good knowledge of language by the researcher, the presence of the so-called linguistic sense.

Observation is an integral part of any scientific activity. Observation is included as a necessary element in the procedure of any linguistic method and technique. Observation has become a popular scientific method of cognition because it allows one to study phenomena in their natural state using the senses and the brain. It differs from experimentation in that it creates artificial conditions and often involves the use of special equipment.

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